
HYPONYMIC RELATIONSHI IN WORDS IN SEMANTICS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848156>

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Annotation .

This article describes the hyponymic taxonomy as an object of the study the semantics and its semantic features in English linguistics. In addition to this, some examples are given with explanations and their taxonomic analysis which is taken as an object of semantic layer. One of the most vital progresses in cognitive understanding of information and the extremely significant devices to classifying vocabulary and performing of the human perception.

Key words.

Hyponymy, hyponymic relations, semantic field, gender and type, taxonomy and taxonomic structure.

Introduction.

Taxonomy (classification) is a specific method of semantic analysis, a set of principles and rules for the classification of linguistic objects [1]. Using many methods, the concept of taxonomy, which is expressed as a function of the taxonomic relations of objects and their attributes, was introduced into the linguistic system [2]. The concept of mutualism is important as a tool of evolutionary theory. Taxonomic relationships have been expressed automatically for many years. R.A. Amsler automatically created a taxonomy for English noun and verb word groups based on dictionary definitions [3]. M.A. Hirst introduced the use of lexical and syntactic patterns representing hyponymic relations [4].

Taxonomy simultaneously includes three types of relationships, namely hypernymy (genus-species), hyponymy (species-genus) and cohyponymy (species-species). In the study of lexical-semantic groups and functional-semantic fields of natural language word groups, it shows the lack of strict consistency and systematicity in the manifestation of hyper-hyponymic relations. In the scientific

typologies of various fields, hyper-hyponymy is a common phenomenon that expands and systematizes the concepts of profession.

Research Methodology. It is well known that a taxonomy (or taxonomical classification) the structure of classifying especially it is a hierarchical classification which means that things are organized according to its groups or types. In addition to this, taxonomy also applies to relationship schemes other than parent-child hierarchies such as network structures. Taxonomies hierarchies may then include a single child with multi-parents, for instance, car might appear with both parents vehicles and steel mechanisms; to some however, this merely means that car is a part of several different taxonomies [5].

Materials and methods There have been many researchers and linguistics scholars who have studied and researched the issues related to hyponymy and hyponymic relation and its lexical and semantic characteristics of hyponyms. Here are some examples of research and references.

Researchers have found that they expressed their own opinions and research works about lexical and semantic features of hyponyms (Krongauz M.A.Semantics., 2001) [6]. And also studies can be found about this hyponyms and its semantical features in Uzbek Associate Professor N.K.Sabirova and N.K.Jumaeva's articles ("Hyponymic Taxonomy In Semantics", 2022) [7]. Addition to this the lexical and semantic peculiarities of hyponyms can be highlighted in (Jumaeva, N. K. 2022. Lexical And Semantic Characteristics Of Hyponomic Relations And Deeply Analyzing Its Features In English Linguistics) [8] and and using in teaching process it (Shorxametov Shotillo Safarovich and Tursuntosh Isroilova 2022.) [9].

Result and discussion. When we come to study and research the hyponymic relations in word, we come across several categories of the researching the hyponymy subtype in this paper, they are following categories which are considered important in analyzing the hyponyms, the first one is ID number of the hypernym; hypernym; general semantic category of the hypernym; hyponym; semantic category of the hyponym; hyponymy subtype derived from the hypernym-hyponym pair. For example, if we can give instance for analyzing the word according to these categories, let's consider the word "soil".

Figure 1. The taxonomic configurations the word "soil".

Given the probability that the tree structure is in an asymmetric state, it can be observed that each lexical unit can have many hyponyms, but they have a single hyperonym. In this taxonomic picture we can see the hyponyms of the "soil", the word "soil" is hyperonym, "acid soil, clay, sand, humus, indian red, laterite, surface soil, desert soil" are considered co-hyponyms and the third layer of the words: "top soil, sub soil, undersoil, sedimentary clay, boulder clay and clunch" are considered hyponyms of "soil". According to categories, it is considered the natural entity in term of general semantic category and it is substance according to specific semantic categories, lastly, according to hyponymy subtype this is composition-based hyponymy. Moreover, the troponomic features of hyponyms can be observed in verbs such as compraring in Uzbek and English languges for example: Also, in English language the verb such as "to speak - to call, to talk, to cheer, to yell, to shout, to murmur, to chatter, to whisper, to babble, to blurt or to chant" and in Uzbek language "gapirmoq - suhbatlashmoq, baqirmoq, pichirlamoq, ming'illamoq, valdiramoq, g'uldiramoq, o'yلامasdan aytmog" are used to express the degrees of verb conditions.

It is clear that the phenomenon of hyponymy is the relationship between a hyperonym and its specific hyponym in the linguistics. A hyponym is more precise and clear word or phrase than hyperonym in the semantic field. In this above mentioned condition we can see the homonymic relation of the color, also blue is considered a hyponym of the color but "Blue" is itself a hypernym of various shades of blue, for instance navy, blue purple, aquamarine and so on.[10] In this place, the word "cloth" describes a category, but the words such as "outwear", "footwear", "headwear" express some subsets of that category, additionally, the word "clothes" is larger term which is called hyperynym with respect to the smaller ones: outwear, footwear, headwear and this smaller one is named a

hyponym with the respect to the larger. Such a hyponym, in turn, may have further subcategories like cowboy boots, rubber boots, timberland boots for which it is a hypernym.

Also, the lexical and hyponymic taxonomy in semantic in linguistics is given in the Uzbek Associate Professor N.K.Sabirova and N.K.Jumaevas' article. [7,8]. The analysis of f hyponymy showed that certain subtypes (e.g. agent-based, patient-based, result-based, method-based, degree-based) closely correlated with process-related semantic categories (e.g. activity, phenomenon, process, change of state). On the other hand, other hyponymy subtypes (e.g. composition-based, technology-based, function-based) were directly linked to entity-related semantic categories (e.g. substance, landform, construction, instrument). Furthermore, the results also demonstrated that a distinction can be made between relational hyponymy subtypes (i.e. those involving another concept, like agent-based, resultbased or location-based) and attributional hyponymy subtypes (i.e. those involving the intrinsic characteristics of the concept, like shape-based, texturebased or moisture-based). Relational hyponymy subtypes were generally associated with processes, whilst attributional hyponymy subtypes were mainly related to entities. In addition, further distinctions were made not only depending on whether concepts were entities or processes, but also between natural and artificial concepts. In this line, some hyponymy subtypes were shown to be mostly exclusive to natural concepts (e.g. origin-based, state-based, time-based), whereas other hyponymy subtypes were generally attributed to artificial concepts (e.g. function-based, technology-based, weight-based).[11] Let's we will consider some examples according to hyponymic categories.

1. Type of hyponymy (transport):
 - a) The ship Titanic was due to leave at half past eleven.
 - b) When they got out of the cart.

A "ship" is defined as a small vessel for travel on water. Vessel is here synonymous to transport. While, "cart" is synonymous open wheeled transport, which is without a doubt it a kind of a transportation. Hence, these two words are classified as transportation hyponymy.

2. Type of hyponymy (transport): "velosiped, traktor, samolyot, mashina, mototsikl, yuk mashina, poyezd, metro" like words in Uzbek language.
 - a) Farmon bibining ikki nabirasiga uch oyoqli velosiped sovg'a qildi.
3. Type of hyponymy (occupation)
 - b) And an old seamen in a jersey command his mariners.

c) Such a very nice stewardess and pilot came to meet the passengers in a plan before flying.

A “sailor and mariners” are a traveler by water while, a stewardess is a woman who performs the duties of a steward, especially one who attends passengers (as on an airplane). The words “seamen and mariner” and “stewardess and pilot” are both types of occupation. Therefore, these two words are categorized as occupation hyponymy.

4. Type of hyponymy (occupation) in Uzbek language: o`qituvchi, farrosh, haydovchi, dehqon

- a) Uning onasi maktabda farrosh edi.
- b) O`qituvchilar majlisda edi.
- c) Dehqon juda qattiq ishlar edi.

There is given the hyponymic relationship of the word according to the subcategory :occupation-based hyponym of the word “profession” in English language. We can see its taxonomic analysis of the word “profession” which is expressed in the below.

Figure 2 . The taxonomic description of the word “profession”

In this place, the word “profession” describes a category , but the words such as “Teacher”, “Fly attendant”, “Cleaner”, “Sailor”, “ Driver”, “Builder” express some subsets of that category of the occupation, additionally, the word “profession” is larger term which is called hypernym with respect to the smaller ones: “Teacher”, “Fly attendant”, “Cleaner”, “Sailor”, “ Driver”, “Builder” and this smaller one is named a hyponym with the respect to the larger. Such a hyponym, in turn, may have further subcategories like “Air hostess”, “Stewardess”, “Shipman”, “Seamen”, “Mariner” for which it is a hypernym.

Also, we can analyzed the other lexical word such as connected with the hyponymic relationship and its semantic features according in order to observe through it hyponymic configuration which is given below.

Figure 3 . The hyponymic description of the word “Human”

In this place, the word “Human” describes a sex-based category or gender-based category in hyponymic relationship in words, but the words such as “Man / Male” and “Woman / Female” express some subsets of that category of the sex or gender, additionally, the word “human” is larger term which is called hypernym with respect to the smaller ones: “Man / Male” and “Woman / Female” and this smaller one is named a hyponym with the respect to the larger. Such a hyponym, in turn, may have further subcategories like “Father, Prince, Gentlemen, King, Boy” and “Girl, Lady, Daughter, Mother, Maiden, Maid” for which it is a hypernym and it is clear that according to these words we can separate its real meaning which belongs to women or men or its gender. In this situation, the meaning of the lexical units can be seen from general to specific or from abstract to concrete or it forms as from top to bottom. In addition to, let’s see next example about this relation of words which are considered the part of the speech: noun and in this hyponymic relations of words that can be used interchangeably in the sentences. According to next examples we can see the meaning of the lexical unit “consumer” will be clear from general to specific.

Figure 4. Hyponomic relation of the lexical unit of "Consumer".

In this place, the word "Consumer" describes a category, but the words such as "Meaterian, Pescaterian, Vegaterian" express some subsets of that category, additionally, the word "consumer" is larger term which is called hypernym with respect to the smaller ones: Meaterian, Pescaterian, Vegaterian and this smaller one is named a hyponym with the respect to the larger. Such a hyponym, in turn, may have further subcategories like "Fishaterian, Vegaquarian, Pescocoveterian" for which it is a hypernym. Let's observe them in the sentences:

The visitors of our restaurants are pescaterian.

The consumers are considered mostly fish eaters in our restaurant.

However, some units represent a "type" diagnostic for hyponymy, but cannot be a suitable example of a syllogism.

Laptop is a type of computer.

A computer is a type of office equipment.

Laptop is a type of office equipment.

Two of the sentences in the given examples contain arguments that do not fit into a syllogism. The word "laptop" in the first sentence is a correct sentence that describes a typical computer. In the second sentence, different functions and criteria of "laptop" can be understood. Another issue of examples 1 and 2 can also be observed, that is, the types of interaction in them cannot be equivalent to each other. The first sentence represents a taxonomic hyponymy or taxonomy sentence which means that what the laptop is, while the second sentence shows what the computer is used for and its function. All terms can have two different types of hyperonyms. For example, the word "giraffe" has two hyperonyms, the taxonomic meaning "animal or living thing" and the functional hyponymy meaning "wild animal". Or another example such as "water" has two hyperonyms, the taxonomic meaning "liquid" and functional hyponymy meaning "drinking liquid". Reciprocity in syllogism is observed only in taxonomic hyponymy.

Conclusion The hyponym and hypernym relationship are very important in giving a logical connection in speech, expressing the meaning of words. There is no

clear basis for the fact that a hyper-hyponymic relationship is a linguistic-lexical relationship rather than a cognitive-semantic relationship. The taxonomies of hyponymy do not cover all types of relationships that fall into the general term. The fact that functional hyponyms do not have to be part of hypernyms, the range of what is considered a hyponym in these taxonomies, suggests that hyponymy is a broad concept. Easy and quick teaching of various terms to young people in teaching English can increase the level of communication in this foreign language and allow them to freely express their opinions in a foreign language.

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